

RAMONES

Radioactivity Monitoring in Ocean Ecosystems

Deliverable

Document ID: D5.4 Repository, Information System and Risk no4

31/01/2024

RAMONES funded by European Union under Horizon 2020 FET Proactive programme via grant agreement No.101017808

Document Info

Project Information			
Acronym	RAMONES		
Name	Radioactivity Monitoring in Ocean Ecosystems		
Start Date	1 Jan 2021	End Date	31 Dec 2024
Program	H2020-EU.1.2.2. - FET Proactive		
Call ID	H2020-FETPROACT-2020-2	Topic	FETPROACT-EIC-08-2020 - Environmental Intelligence
Grant No	101017808	Instrument	RIA
Document Information			
Document Id	D5.4		
Document Title	D5.4 Repository, Information System and Risk no4		
Due Date	31-Dec-2023	Delivery Date	31-Jan-2024
Lead Beneficiary	UDUR(1)		
Beneficiaries (part.)	UDUR(1), ENS(2), UCA(3)		
Editor(s)	Konstantinos Nikolopoulos (UDUR)		
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Contributor (s)			
Reviewer(s)	NKUA		
Workpackages	WP5 - Citizen Awareness, Dissemination and Communication Activities		
Version	V1.0	Stage	TOC
Distribution	Public		
Keywords	Pathfinder, EIC, FET, Radioactivity, Environmental Intelligence, Underwater Research	Type	R

Document Change Record

Version	Date	Change Description	Editor	Change Location (page/section)
1.0	09/11/2022	Presentation made in GoodIT22	UDUR	
	03/01/2024	Alpha Testing of POIS2ON Prototype Information System	UDUR	
	26/01/2024	Beta Testing of POIS2ON Prototype Information System	UDUR, NKUA	
	28/01/2024	Document delivered to key authors	UDUR, NKUA	
	30/01/2024	Document delivered to all authors	UDUR	
1.29	31/01/2024	Feedback implemented and document, plus link to information system POISSON submitted to funder	UDUR	

Disclaimer

RAMONES is a European Innovation Council (EIC) FET Proactive project in the Environmental Intelligence Scope B, related to radically novel approaches to resilient, reliable and environmentally responsible in-situ monitoring. It is funded by the European Union under the Horizon 2020 FET proactive programme, via grant agreement No. 101017808.

RAMONES project's main objective is to close the current marine radioactivity gap in sampling and foster new interdisciplinary research in ocean ecosystems. RAMONES will invest a significant effort to provide tools to enable long-term data acquisition missions, rapid deployments, low cost per information byte, and propose new AI and Robotics-driven and supported methodologies, being ambitious to eventually offer scaled-up solutions to researchers, policy makers and communities. These goals will be achieved by combining state-of-the-art methodologies and equipment from various disciplines in a well-balanced synergy. It will also design new and effective methodologies targeting the marine environment, which will provide efficient response to existing natural and man-made hazards, and shape future policies for the global population. RAMONES will additionally contribute to shaping a blueprint on Environmental Intelligence in the EU and worldwide.

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List of acronyms

Acronym	Description
AI	Artificial Intelligence
DB	Database
EIC	European Innovation Council
EU	European Union
F2SS	Forecasting & Foresight Support System
FSS	Forecasting Support Systems
GIS	Geographical Information System
ML	Machine Learning
POIS2ON	Prototype RAMONES Information System for SocioecONomic stakeholders
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
WP	Work Package

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Abstract

RAMONES is an ambitious, high-risk FET H2020 project which aims to achieve high-resolution temporal and spatial underwater AI-driven radioactivity measurements, in situ and in near-real-time, forming a game changer in deep-water environmental monitoring. RAMONES proposes a new generation of submarine radiation-sensing instruments, assisted by State of the Art robotic and artificial intelligence solutions towards understanding radiation related risks near and far from coastal areas, while providing data for the international community towards shaping new policies and governance guidelines for environmental sustainability, economic growth, and human health.

One of the main goals also of RAMONES is to introduce novel monitoring and response channels to **inform key socio-political and socio-economic stakeholders** at regular intervals at medium (hourly, daily, weekly) to low (monthly to inter-annually) frequencies. To that end, the deliverable **5.4. of Work Package 5 provides the prototype information system, POIS2ON** (Prototype RAMONES Information System for SocioecONomic stakeholders).

POIS2ON provides statistical and ML forecasts for radionuclide concentrations at high frequency (every 10ms) in the sea as well as respective instantaneous and cumulative risks. At a second stage and once Risk Indices have been fully developed too (deliverables D5.7 – D5.8) full risk awareness capabilities will be added to the system. Finally, provision for spatio-temporal representation and visualization will be prescribed via connections to a GIS system (Geographical Information Systems), as well as links to a system developed by UCA that simulates and calculates absorbed dosages from microorganisms and humans (D5.8).

Keywords

RAMONES; POIS2ON; Radioactivity; Deep Water; Information System; Forecasting; Risk.

1. Introduction

1.1 Context

This document belongs to Work Package 5 (WP5, *Citizen Awareness, Communication and Dissemination Activities*), and in particular to Task T5.1 *Forecasting and risk management* led by UDUR that is aiming to transliterate the in-situ, high frequency of radioactivity in deep ocean waters to actual time series that can be forecasted, estimating when general acceptable daily/weekly/monthly/annually limits are reached/exceeded, and as such quantify the risk and potential impact to the environment and human populations.

1.2 Structure of the document

From this point, the current document is organized according to the following structure and contents:

Section 2. Basic Usage Scenario of POIS2ON

Section 3. The POIS2ON prototype system

Section 4. Conclusion and the Future

1.3 Objectives and approach

The objectives of the RAMONES D5.4 deliverable is to deliver a **full working version** of the prototype system **POIS2ON**.

2. Basic usage Scenario

In the **basic usage scenario**, the assumption is that a living organisation (human or not) is **receiving instantaneously a large radiation dosage** and we examine the chance of receiving (or emitting) in one go the entire annual dosage or more. That will happen by randomly passing from an affected area and it could happen in as fast a 10ms. **As such we observe and forecast times series at this high frequency for single elements and/or the full spectrum**. The cumulative scenario where the living organisation lays for a large amount of time in a (less) affected area, and gradually received withing that time frame the annual dosage, will be examined in deliverable D5.7.

3. The prototype POISSON system

The system is prescribed by the functional requirements et in **D5.1**, the design set in **D5.2**, and the DB set in **D5.3**. It also includes already elements of **D5.5** and **D5.6** that will be fully operational once D5.7 is due (month 42) as well as link to GIS capabilities in D5.8 (due M48).

The Alpha testing of the **POISSON** system took place in December 2023 and January 2024 while the Beta testing took place the last week of January 2024 with promising feedback and performance.

There is already a **Repository** in place where data from the Ramones project are securely hosted at NKUA via the effective and stable ELOG system, hosted on the address:

<http://radium.phys.uoa.gr:8080/ramones>

accessed from anywhere in the world. Access and passwords for the repository can be provided via the RAMONES Principal Investigator.

Figure 1 – Repository of RAMONES

The actual POIS2ON system developed with R, R shiny, Python, and MySQL, is currently running from a Google VM on the address:

<http://34.142.73.98:3838/Pois2on/>

accessed from anywhere in the world. At the end of the project there is provision for POIS2ON to be transferred to two servers, one in UDUR and one in NKUA where it will run in secure servers of the two academic institutions. Access to POIS2ON at the aforementioned URL address is done with the:

Username: Ramones

Password: Gnikol2907

There is also a series of administrative passwords for the system that are held by UDUR. This latter information will be redacted in the version of the deliverable available in the public via the project dedicated website.

The remaining of this section is dedicated to the interface of POIS2ON and respective screenshots, as follows:

In figure 2 we see the initial webpage of the application:

Figure 2 – Secure Entrance to POIS2ON

Repository, Information System and Risk no2

In figure 3 we see the landing page once we pass security. There are five main choices – the standalone version that reads one file (xls/csv/xlsx) and on the fly runs forecasts and visualizations. Then there are two options to navigate through the SQL Database and two options to link to other applications (GIS and Dosage Rates SQL respectively). In the main landing page, there are two tabs – one for forecasting and one for risk management (essentially holding elements of the RMIS system – see D5.2).

Figure 3 – Main screen and respective functionality of POIS2ON

Repository, Information System and Risk no2

In figure 4 we see the full screen from top to bottom where the map is also visible where we can see the location where the measurement took place (automatically via the longitude, latitude information in the csv/xls/xlsx file).

Figure 4 – Full main screen of POIS2ON (Top to Bottom)

Repository, Information System and Risk no2

In figure 5 we see that we can have two (or more) sessions of the system open at the same time running effortlessly and smoothly.

Figure 5 – Forecasting with the Theta method for the Full spectrum of (simulated data) from Kolumbo in a second session opened in parallel with first one (multiple users).

Repository, Information System and Risk no2

In figure 6 we see the format of the csv/xlx/xlsx file that is necessary for the input of the data from any other application or in real time from the sensors an instruments and devices of RAMONES – any incoming information to POIS2ON needs to be converted to this standard and easy format. It can contain as many elements as the user wants.

1	Location	Lon	Lat	Depth	Instrument	Date	Time	Cs.237	Ra.226	Pb.214	Pu.240	Full_Spectrum
2	Kolombo, Greece	25.49072028	36.52560719	18	Gaspar	08/01/2024	0	51.6	30.33	49.47	49.31	180.71
3	Kolombo, Greece	25.49072028	36.52560719	18	Gaspar	08/01/2024	10	55.97	47.11	50.2	48.91	202.19
4	Kolombo, Greece	25.49072028	36.52560719	18	Gaspar	08/01/2024	20	49.85	35.23	52.27	53.28	190.63
5	Kolombo, Greece	25.49072028	36.52560719	18	Gaspar	08/01/2024	30	51.53	40.57	48.17	36.84	177.11
6	Kolombo, Greece	25.49072028	36.52560719	18	Gaspar	08/01/2024	40	44.9	38.77	42.61	55.02	181.3
7	Kolombo, Greece	25.49072028	36.52560719	18	Gaspar	08/01/2024	50	44.9	28.73	33.46	49.47	156.56
8	Kolombo, Greece	25.49072028	36.52560719	18	Gaspar	08/01/2024	60	39.55	40.5	37.32	27.93	145.3
9	Kolombo, Greece	25.49072028	36.52560719	18	Gaspar	08/01/2024	70	41.95	32.83	47.28	41.37	163.43
10	Kolombo, Greece	25.49072028	36.52560719	18	Gaspar	08/01/2024	80	36.33	29.21	44.19	30.95	140.68
11	Kolombo, Greece	25.49072028	36.52560719	18	Gaspar	08/01/2024	90	32.06	38.77	42.44	43.42	156.69
12	Kolombo, Greece	25.49072028	36.52560719	18	Gaspar	08/01/2024	100	37.29	50.63	46.15	39.12	173.19
13	Kolombo, Greece	25.49072028	36.52560719	18	Gaspar	08/01/2024	110	40.94	36.63	45	46.04	168.61
14	Kolombo, Greece	25.49072028	36.52560719	18	Gaspar	08/01/2024	120	41.37	32.22	55.2	56.99	185.78
15	Kolombo, Greece	25.49072028	36.52560719	18	Gaspar	08/01/2024	130	32.72	45.17	35.29	38.06	151.24
16	Kolombo, Greece	25.49072028	36.52560719	18	Gaspar	08/01/2024	140	11.63	49.03	11.52	37.33	109.51
17	Kolombo, Greece	25.49072028	36.52560719	18	Gaspar	08/01/2024	150	35.44	48.86	42.74	52.99	180.03
18	Kolombo, Greece	25.49072028	36.52560719	18	Gaspar	08/01/2024	160	31.24	28.84	52.28	46.93	159.29
19	Kolombo, Greece	25.49072028	36.52560719	18	Gaspar	08/01/2024	170	37.3	37.55	47.74	35.91	158.5
20	Kolombo, Greece	25.49072028	36.52560719	18	Gaspar	08/01/2024	180	23.83	54.99	36.3	58.93	174.05
21	Kolombo, Greece	25.49072028	36.52560719	18	Gaspar	08/01/2024	190	41.17	35.38	34.1	37.33	147.98

Figure 6 – Standard .csv/.xls/.xlsx Input file for POIS2ON

Repository, Information System and Risk no2

In figure 7 we see how we open a new file to load data; by default, the file 'testdata.xls' is opened (if it exists in the directory of the application).

Figure 7 – Opening new .csv/.xls/.xlsx Input file for POISZON

Repository, Information System and Risk no2

In figure 8 we see what happens when we ask the application to transfer the data from the input file to the SQL database.

The screenshot shows the RAMONES PoiSZon web application. A modal window titled "Important message" is centered on the screen, displaying the text "The data have been saved to the database." Below the message is a "CLOSE" button. The background interface includes a "UPLOAD" button, a table of data points, and a forecasting graph. The table has columns for "Address", "Lat", "Depth", "Instrument", and "Date". The graph shows "Full Spectrum" on the y-axis and "Time" on the x-axis, with a black line for recorded data and a blue line for forecasts.

Address	Lat	Depth	Instrument	Date
Kolonbe, Greece	36.52860719	18	Gaspar	8/1/2024
Milos, Greece	25.49072028	36.91321	ASPECT	10/1/2024

Figure 8 – Saving from new .csv/.xls/.xlsx Input file to the SQL Database in POIS2ON

In figure 9 we see the first seven (7) methods that the user can select to forecast the dataset [R 2024]: the Theta model, Simple Exponential Smoothing, the Naïve method, the Seasonal Naïve method, a simple Average, Naive with a Drift, Splines.

Figure 9 – Selection of Forecasting method in POIS2ON – Part 1

Repository, Information System and Risk no2

In figure 10 we see the remaining four (4) methods that the user can select to forecast the dataset [R 2024]: the Holt Exponential Smoothing, the ETS method, the famous ARIMA method as the most established benchmark in such empirical forecasting competitions and one ML method that of Artificial Neural Networks.

Figure 10 – Selection of Forecasting method in POIS2ON – Part 2

Repository, Information System and Risk no2

In figure 11 we see the forecasts provided by the ML method.

Figure 11 – Forecasting with an ML method (ANN) in POIS2ON

Repository, Information System and Risk no2

In figure 12 we see application to visualise the locations where the measurements have been taken (by reading the longitude and latitude).

Figure 12 – Automatic linking of the data to a Map in POIS2ON

In figure 13 we see the application linking to the code used to calculate the Risk Index at any given moment (in Python).

Figure 13 – Linking to the Python code for Risk Analysis in POIS2ON. Full integration of code in R and link to the RMIS (D5.6) in D5.7

Repository, Information System and Risk no2

In figure 14 we can see that we can open directly the code in Python to run (in a separate application) the calculation of the Risk Index.

Figure 14 – Python code for Risk Analysis in POIS2ON. Full integration of code in R and link to the RMIS (D5.6) in D5.7

Repository, Information System and Risk no2

In figure 15 we see the schema of the SQL database.

Figure 15 – Database View (SQL) – Schema – in POIS2ON

In figure 16 we see how we can retrieve data from the database.

Table name: devices	
device_id	device_name
1	Wave Glider 1
2	Wave Glider 2
3	Surface Vehicle
4	ROV

Table name: elements	
element_id	element_name
1	Cs-237
2	Rn-22
3	Ra-226
4	Pb-214
5	Pb-210

Table name: instruments	
instrument_id	instrument_name
1	Gaspar
2	gama-Sniffer 1
3	gama-Sniffer 2
4	aSPECT
5	CHERI

Table name: measurement_master											
instrument_id	time	depth	lat	lon	source_id	element_id	unit_id	device_id	site_id	measurement_id	duration
No data available in table											

Table name: measurement_spectrum		
measurement_id	frequency	measurement
No data available in table		

Table name: sites	
site_id	site_name
1	Milos, Greece
2	Kolombo, Greece
3	Marseille, France

Table name: sources	
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Table name: units	
-------------------	--

Figure 16 – Retrieval of data from the tables of the SQL Database in POIS2ON

In figure 17 we see how we can run forecasts in the SQL mode. For the sake of consistency, the UI (User Interface) is identical.

Figure 17 – Running the forecasting on data retrieved from the SQL database; rather than on the fly from the csv/xls/xlsx file in POIS2ON

Repository, Information System and Risk no2

In figure 18 we see the future connection with a GIS system.

Figure 18 – Future link to GIS in POIS2ON (in D5.8)

Repository, Information System and Risk no2

In figure 19 we see the future connection with the Dosage Rates simulation software developed by UCA in HeidiSQL.

Figure 19 – Future link to Dosage Rates software developed by UCA in POIS2ON (in D5.8)

In figure 20 we see the link to the RAMONES project website.

Figure 20 – Link to the RAMONES project website in POIS2ON

In figure 21 we see the RAMONES website as redirected from POIS2ON.

Figure 21 – Redirection to the RAMONES project website in POIS2ON

Repository, Information System and Risk no2

In figure 22 we see the specs of the mobile device (Laptop) that was used to run the application. As this is a web application it is very light and test have run with i3 with 4GB of RAM and we saw no difference in the performance. Texts are dur once the size of the database becomes substantially larger as queries will require the speed of the CPU as such.

Figure 22 – Actual Specs of the Laptop that run POIS2ON in D5.4

In figure 23 we see the specs of the mobile device (Android Phone) that was used to run the application. As this is a web application it is very light, and test have run smoothly in a mobile phone too.

Figure 23 – Actual Specs of the Mobile Phone that run POIS2ON in D5.4

In figure 24 we see two instances of POIS2ON *logging in* at the same time, one in a laptop and one in a mobile phone.

Figure 24 – Parallel log in of two devices (mobile and laptop) that run POIS2ON in D5.4

In figure 25 we see two instances of POIS2ON *running* at the same time, one in a laptop and one in a mobile phone.

Figure 25 – Parallel running in of two devices (mobile and laptop) that run POIS2ON in D5.4

In figure 26 we see two instances of POIS2ON forecasting at the same time, one in a laptop and one in a mobile phone.

Figure 26 – Parallel forecasting in two devices (mobile and laptop) that run POIS2ON in D5.4

4. Conclusion and the Future

RAMONES aspires to introduce novel monitoring and response channels to inform key socio-political and socio-economics stakeholders at regular intervals at medium (daily, weekly) to low (monthly to inter-annually) frequencies. To that end, the deliverable **D5.4** of Work Package 5 **provides the prototype information system POIS2ON.**

POIS2ON provides **statistical and ML forecasts** for radionuclide concentrations in the sea, as well as respective instantaneous and cumulative risks. At a second stage and once Risk Indices have been fully developed too (deliverables D5.7 – D5.8) foresight capabilities will be added to the system (functional requirements provided in D5.5 and Python implementation in D5.6) leading to a complete Forecasting & Foresight Support System (F2SS) given the long-term nature of such activities. Finally, provision for spatio-temporal representation and visualization will be prescribed via connections to a GIS system (Geographical Information Systems), as well as links to a system developed by UCA that simulates and calculates absorbed dosages from microorganisms and humans (D5.8). For the immediate next steps, we also plan in D5.7 to integrate Risk Management facilities as well Cumulative Series facilities in POIS2ON rather than keep separate information systems.

5. Acknowledgements

The primary author (UDUR) thanks for, and acknowledge the support of

- **Professor Dimitrios Thomakos (NKUA)** ([Dimitrios Thomakos | IMC Laboratory \(uoa.gr\)](#)) for his insights in the selection of forecasting methods and risk indices,
- **Dr Evangelos Theodorou** ([Evangelos THEODOROU | Research Fellow | Diploma \(MEng\), DEng | National Technical University of Athens, Athens | NTUA | School of Electrical and Computer Engineering | Research profile \(researchgate.net\)](#)) for his support and advice in the POIS2ON implementation with R, R shiny, Python, and MySQL and the integration of the RMIS into POIS2ON.

6. References

[R 2024] R package FORECAST <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/forecast/index.html>